

MICROMECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF STIFFNESS REDUCTION OF CERAMIC/CERAMIC COMPOSITES WITH INTERFACIAL PHENOMENA

Kenji SAITO, Shigetoshi ARAKI, and Masaharu IWAMOTO

Department of Mechanical and System Engineering, Kyoto Institute of Technology
Matsugasaki, Sakyo-ku, Kyoto, 606, JAPAN

ABSTRACT

The micromechanical analysis is performed on the stiffness reduction of ceramic/ceramic composites in which the large matrix micro-cracks and the interfacial sliding between a fiber and a matrix coexist. By introducing the distribution of the length of matrix crack to the analytical model of such composites, the criteria for the propagation and arrest to each crack can be derived in terms of both the energy release rate for a crack and the energy dissipation occurred by the interfacial sliding. The macroscopic compliance at the given applied stress can be derived from the current distribution of the crack length by using the criteria. The results obtained can be successfully explained the stiffness reduction of such composites.

Keywords: Micromechanics, Inhomogeneity, Eigenstrain, Composites, Bridging Fiber, Stiffness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have a significant feature that the overall mechanical properties as composites are different from those of each constitutive materials. For instance, a ceramic/ceramic composites will not fail in a *brittle* manner but in a rather *ductile* one, in some cases, although all of constitutive elements of such composites are brittle. The *ductile* behavior is considered to be due to the interfacial phenomena between a fiber and a matrix. Thus, for the problem to evaluate the mechanical properties of composites, it is necessary to consider the interfacial phenomena in addition to the micro-structure of the composites. Micromechanics is one of the powerful methods to solve such a problem successfully [1]. The present paper deals with the micromechanical analysis on the stiffness reduction of ceramic/ceramic composites in which the so-called large matrix micro-cracks and the interfacial sliding between a fiber and a matrix coexist.

2. MODELING AND ANALYSIS

2.1. Modeling Of Bridging Fiber In A Matrix

The geometrical modeling of bridging fibers in a matrix [2] is shown in Figure 1. The fiber whose longitudinal axis is parallel to the loading axis is a prolate spheroid with a length $2l$ and a radius $2r$. This fiber region is denoted by Ω_f . It may be assumed that there are n cracks whose surfaces are perpendicular to the loading axis in a matrix.

(a) case of $\alpha_1 = 0$

(b) case of $\alpha_1 \neq 0$

Figure 1. Modeling of bridging fiber. Figure 2. Distortion of crack bridging region.

Every crack is a penny-shape with the same thickness $2C$. However, the radii of the cracks are various. These radii are classified by the length and denoted by a_i . The number of the suffix is labeled in reverse order in accordance with the crack length, namely,

$$a_1 > a_2 > a_3 > \dots > a_{p-1} > a_p \quad (1)$$

Furthermore, the numbers of each crack a_i is defined by n_{c_i} . Thus we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^p n_{c_i} = n_c \quad (2)$$

The region of a crack-bridging fiber is assumed to be approximately a penny-shape with a radius r and a thickness $2C$. The crack region and the crack bridging fiber one are denoted by Ω_{c_i} and Ω_{o_i} , respectively. The volume fraction of fiber is f , and that of crack region Ω_{c_i} is defined by the crack density ρ_i [3],

$$\rho_i = \frac{1}{V_D} \frac{4}{3} \pi a_i^3 n_{c_i} \quad (3)$$

where V_D is the total volume of the system. Then the volume fraction of a crack bridging fiber region Ω_{o_i} is equal to $\rho_i f$ [4].

By applying the inclusion modeling of the micromechanics to the crack region Ω_{c_i} and the crack bridging fiber one Ω_{o_i} , the eigenstrains are given as follows:

$$(\epsilon_{33}^{*c})_i \quad \text{in } \Omega_{c_i} \quad , \quad -(1 - \alpha_i)(\epsilon_{33}^{*c})_i \quad \text{in } \Omega_{o_i} \quad (4)$$

The distortion of the crack bridging fiber region according to α_i are shown in Figure 2. From these eigenstrains, the eigenstresses in Ω_{c_i} and Ω_{o_i} are given as follows:

$$\sigma_{11}^{\infty}(\Omega_{c_i}) = -\frac{\pi\mu(1+2\nu)}{4(1-\nu)} \frac{c}{a_i} (\varepsilon_{33}^{*c})_i, \quad \sigma_{33}^{\infty}(\Omega_{c_i}) = -\frac{\pi\mu}{2(1-\nu)} \frac{c}{a_i} (\varepsilon_{33}^{*c})_i, \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{11}^{\infty}(\Omega_{o_i}) = \frac{\pi\mu(1+2\nu)}{4(1-\nu)} \frac{c}{r} (1-\alpha_i)(\varepsilon_{33}^{*c})_i, \quad \sigma_{33}^{\infty}(\Omega_{o_i}) = \frac{\pi\mu}{2(1-\nu)} \frac{c}{r} (1-\alpha_i)(\varepsilon_{33}^{*c})_i. \quad (6)$$

2.2. Modified Equivalent Inclusion Method

Under the uniform external stress σ_{ij}^0 whose direction is parallel to the fiber one, the modified equivalent expression in Ω_f is

$$\sigma_{ij}^0 + \tilde{\sigma}_{ij} + \sigma_{ij}^{\infty}(\Omega_f) = C_{ijkl}^f (\varepsilon_{kl}^0 + \tilde{\varepsilon}_{kl} + S_{klmn}^f \varepsilon_{mn}^{*f}) = C_{ijkl} (\varepsilon_{kl}^0 + \tilde{\varepsilon}_{kl} + S_{klmn}^f \varepsilon_{mn}^{*f} - \varepsilon_{kl}^{*f}), \quad (7)$$

where

- C_{ijkl}, C_{ijkl}^f : elastic constant of a matrix and a fiber,
- $\sigma_{ij}^0, \varepsilon_{ij}^0$: applied stress and strain, where $\sigma_{ij}^0 = C_{ijkl} \varepsilon_{kl}^0$,
- $\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}, \tilde{\varepsilon}_{ij}$: interaction field, where $\tilde{\sigma}_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \tilde{\varepsilon}_{kl}$,
- ε_{ij}^{*f} : equivalent eigenstrain in Ω_f ,
- S_{ijkl}^f : Eshelby's tensor for a fiber,
- $\sigma_{ij}^{\infty}(\Omega_f)$: eigenstress caused by a inclusion Ω_f .

The equivalent eigenstrain and eigenstress in Ω_f can be obtained from Equation 7.

2.3. Conditions To The Sum Of Internal Stress And Over The Crack Surface

As the integral of internal stress over the whole body is equal to zero, thus the interaction stress is obtained as follows:

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{ij} = -\left\{ f \sigma_{ij}^{\infty}(\Omega_f) + \sum_{l=1}^p \rho_l f \sigma_{ij}^{\infty}(\Omega_{o_l}) + \sum_{l=1}^p \rho_l \sigma_{ij}^{\infty}(\Omega_{c_l}) \right\}, \quad (8)$$

in terms of the volume fraction and eigenstress of each region. Since the stress over the crack surface is free, then we have

$$\sigma_{33}^0 + \sigma_{33}^{\infty}(\Omega_{c_i}) + \tilde{\sigma}_{33} = 0. \quad (9)$$

The interaction stress $\tilde{\sigma}_{33}$ is constant in the system under the constant applied stress, thus, from Equations 5, 6, 8, and 9, the eigenstrain of the crack becomes

$$\frac{(\varepsilon_{33}^{*c})_i}{a_i} = \frac{2(1-\nu)}{\pi\mu c} \frac{\sigma_{33}^0 - f \sigma_{33}^{\infty}(\Omega_f)}{\phi}, \quad \phi = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^p \rho_i + f \sum_{i=1}^p (1-\alpha_i) \rho_i \frac{a_i}{r}. \quad (10)$$

From the above equations, the stress and strain in each region can be determined. Finally, the eigenstrain of the crack is given as follows:

$$\frac{(\varepsilon_{33}^{*c})_i}{a_i} = \frac{2(1-\nu)}{\pi\mu c} \xi \sigma_{33}^0, \quad \xi = \frac{1-fF_3}{\phi}. \quad (11)$$

Figure 3. Modeling of interfacial sliding.

2.4. Modeling Of Interfacial Sliding

The model of the interfacial sliding between a fiber and a matrix is shown in Figure 3. The friction stress k of the interface is assumed to be constant from the crack surface to the border $A-A'$ in the figure. When the range of sliding is prescribed by δ , we have

$$\sigma_{33}^{\infty}(\Omega_{o_i}) + \sigma_{33}^{\infty}(\Omega_{c_i}) = 2 \frac{\delta}{r} k \quad , \quad (12)$$

considering the equilibrium of force. Substituting Equations 5, 6, and 11 into Equation 12, we have

$$\alpha_i = 1 - \frac{r}{a_i} \left(1 + \frac{R_0}{\xi} \right) \quad , \quad R_0 = 2 \frac{\delta k}{r \sigma_{33}^o} \quad . \quad (13)$$

Since the distance of sliding is equal to the crack opening displacement $2c\alpha_i (\epsilon_{33}^{*c})_i$, the dissipation energy due to sliding can be obtained as

$$W_{d_i} = 2 \pi r \delta k \times 2c \alpha_i (\epsilon_{33}^{*c})_i \times n_{o_i} \quad , \quad (14)$$

where n_{o_i} is the numbers of crack bridging region Ω_{o_i} in Ω_{c_i} .

2.5. Definitions Of Parameter m And ρ_n

The value of α_i controlling the crack opening due to sliding is assumed to be

$$\alpha_i \neq 0 \quad 1 \leq i \leq m \quad , \quad \alpha_i = 0 \quad m < i \leq p \quad . \quad (15)$$

It is obvious from this definition that the cracks having larger suffix number than m are not in the state indicated in Figure 2(b). By using Equation 15, ϕ in Equation 10 becomes, finally,

$$\phi = \frac{\phi_A}{\phi_B} = \frac{1 - f \rho_n \{(\beta_3)_1^p - f(\beta_4)_1^p\} + f \rho_n \{R_7(\beta_3)_1^m - (\beta_4)_1^m\}}{1 - f \rho_n R_6(\beta_3)_1^m} , \quad (16)$$

where

$$\sum_{i=1}^p \left(\frac{a_i}{r} \right)^q \left(\frac{n_{c_i}}{n_c} \right) = (\beta_q)_1^p , \quad (\beta_q)_1^0 = 0 , \quad \rho_n = \frac{1}{V_D} \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 n_c . \quad (17)$$

It is obvious from the above equation that ρ_n is the parameter which has one-to-one correspondence to the total crack number n_c .

2.6. Energy Release Rates

The total potential energy F caused only by the variation of eigenstrain is defined as

$$F = -\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_f} \sigma_{33}^o \varepsilon_{33}^{*f} dD - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^p \left[\int_{\Omega_{c_i}} \sigma_{33}^o (\varepsilon_{33}^{*c})_i dD - \int_{\Omega_{o_i}} \sigma_{33}^o (1 - \alpha_i) (\varepsilon_{33}^{*c})_i dD + \int_{\Omega_{o_i}} \{ \sigma_{33}^{\infty}(\Omega_{o_i}) + \sigma_{33}^{\infty}(\Omega_f) \} \alpha_i (\varepsilon_{33}^{*c})_i dD \right] . \quad (18)$$

By using the definition of Equation 17 and the previous results, we have, finally,

$$F = -\frac{V_D}{2\mu} (\sigma_{33}^o)^2 \frac{2(1-\nu)}{\pi} \left\{ \frac{\pi f}{2(1-\nu)} Q_3 + \xi(1-f) \rho_n (\beta_3)_1^p + \xi f \eta \rho_n (\beta_3)_1^m - f(R_0 + \xi) \eta \rho_n (\beta_2)_1^m \right\} . \quad (19)$$

Similarly, the complementary energy per unit volume W_c / V_D is obtained as follows:

$$\frac{W_c}{V_D} = \frac{(\sigma_{33}^o)^2}{4(1+\nu)\mu} \left[1 + 2(1+\nu)fQ_3 + \frac{4(1-\nu^2)}{\pi} \rho_n \{ \xi(1-f)(\beta_3)_1^p + f\eta\theta \} \right] . \quad (20)$$

The energy release rate for a matrix crack and that for the sliding are defined by

$$G_i = -\frac{\partial F}{\partial (\pi a_i^2)} \left(\frac{1}{n_{c_i}} \right) , \quad \Delta G_i = \frac{\partial W_{d_i}}{\partial (\pi a_i^2)} . \quad (21)$$

Substituting Equations 14 and 19 into Equation 21, we can have the expressions for ΔG_i and G_i , respectively.

By adopting *Griffith's* concept of brittle fracture to the present model, the criterion for the propagation and arrest to each crack becomes

$$G_i - (\Delta G_i + 2\gamma_c) \geq 0 , \quad (22)$$

where γ_c is the surface energy of a matrix. The total energy release rate is defined as

$$G_i^{total} = \{ G_i - (\Delta G_i + 2\gamma_c) \} \frac{n_{c_i}}{n_c} . \quad (23)$$

From this definition, the crack having the largest G_i^{total} in the system will be considered to propagate.

2.7. Macroscopic Compliance

The macroscopic compliance \bar{C} at the given applied stress can be obtained by

$$\bar{C} = \frac{\partial (\epsilon_{33})_{ave}}{\partial \sigma_{33}^o} \quad , \quad (\epsilon_{33})_{ave} = \frac{\partial (W_c / V_D)}{\partial \sigma_{33}^o} \quad , \quad (24)$$

where $(\epsilon_{33})_{ave}$ is the average strain of the composites. By substituting Equation 20 into Equation 24, the compliance \bar{C} can be calculated.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Elastic Properties And Initial Distribution Of Crack Length

In the present research, the discontinuous SiC ceramic fiber-reinforced Borosilicate glass-ceramic is used for sample material of the composites under consideration. The aspect ratio of the fiber is taken 100. Elastic properties of these constitutive materials are listed in Table 1. The initial distribution of the crack length is shown in Figure 4.

In numerical analysis, the energy release rate for a crack with a radius r in a matrix,

$$G_r = \frac{2(1-\nu)}{\pi \mu} (\sigma_{33}^o)^2 r \quad , \quad (25)$$

is introduced as a reference value.

Table 1. Elastic properties of matrix and fiber.

	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio
Matrix (Borosilicate)	60.0	0.20
Fiber (SiC)	427.0	0.20

Figure 4. Initial distribution of the crack length.

3.2. Procedure Of Numerical Analysis

First, the value of m in Equation 15 must be determined. From Equations 11 and 13, α_i is the function of ϕ , and the relation between ϕ and m is given by Equation 16. Since the value of m can hardly be derived analytically from these relations, the numerical analysis is employed.

The flow of the analysis is listed as follows:

- (1) Determination of m from the distribution of the crack length.
- (2) Calculation of the total energy release rate G_i^{total} for every crack.
- (3) Determination of the crack having the largest G_i^{total} .
This crack region is denoted by $\Omega_{c_{\text{max}}}$.
- (4) If the largest G_i^{total} is larger than zero, go to step(8).
- (5) Calculation of the macroscopic compliance \bar{C} .
- (6) Drafting of the macroscopic stress-strain curve by using the compliance \bar{C} .
- (7) After increasing the applied stress, return to step(1).
- (8) After increasing the crack length of the region $\Omega_{c_{\text{max}}}$, return to step(1).

3.3. Numerical Results

Macroscopic stress-strain curves to various volume fractions of fiber f are shown in Figure 5. The vertical axis is taken to be the applied stress σ_{33}^0 normalized by the friction stress k of the interface, and the horizontal one is the macroscopic average strain $\bar{\epsilon}_{33}$ calculated by the compliance \bar{C} . The dotted lines in the figure show the range that the sum of the crack density $\sum \rho_i$ is larger than unity.

It can be seen from the figure that the stress-strain relations thus obtained show the non-linear behavior irrespective of the volume fractions of fiber f . However, the behavior of the stress-strain curve is considered to be an excessive *ductile* one. In the present model, the coalescence of cracks is out of consideration. Therefore, even if the composites is filled up by the cracks, the composites will never rupture. This is the reason for the extreme *ductility* in the results. By consideration of the definition of crack density ρ_i , we should define the limit of the sum of the crack density $\sum \rho_i$ as unity. The marked points on each curves in the figure show these limits. These points are interpreted as the rupture points of the material from the above discussions.

It can be also seen from the figure that the strain at the rupture point increases with the increase of f . In addition to this fact, the stiffness of the composites increases as the value of f increases. Since these results are consistent with common experimental facts, we think that

Figure 5. Macroscopic stress-strain curve (parameter f) .

Figure 6. Macroscopic stress-strain curve (parameter ρ_n) .

the stiffness reduction of the ceramic/ceramic composites with interfacial sliding can be explained by the present model.

The results of the stress-strain curve to the parameter ρ_n corresponding to the total number of cracks are shown in Figure 6. Only the range that $\sum \rho_i \leq 1$ is shown in the figure. It can be seen from these results that the non-linearity in the stress-strain curve does not appear in the case for the composites containing many cracks. This cause seems to be obvious already from the above discussions.

4. CONCLUSION

The micromechanical analysis is performed on the stiffness reduction of a ceramic/ceramic composites with the large matrix micro-cracks and the interfacial sliding. The macroscopic non-linear stress-strain curves obtained are consistent with common experimental facts. Thus it can be concluded that the stiffness reduction of such composites can be obtained by using the present method.

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